

Interaction of N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines with Ru(0) : Synthesis, structure and, spectral and electrochemical properties of the resulting complexes[†]

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Abstract : Reaction of N-(4'-R-phenyl)pyrrole-2-aldimines (HL-R, where H represents the pyrrole N-H hydrogen and, R = OCH₃, CH₃, H and Cl) with [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃] in refluxing toluene affords a group of yellow complexes of type [Ru(L-R)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)], in which the imine-ligand (L-R) is coordinated to the metal center as a mono-anionic bidentate NN-donor along with two triphenylphosphines, a carbonyl and a hydride. The hydride is *trans* to the coordinated imine-nitrogen, while the carbonyl is *trans* to the pyrrole-nitrogen, and the two triphenylphosphines are mutually *trans*. The hydrido complexes are formed via ruthenium(0) mediated N-H bond activation of the imine ligands. Structure of the [Ru(L-CH₃)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)] complex has been determined by X-ray crystallography. All the complexes are diamagnetic, and show characteristic ¹H NMR signals and intense transitions in the visible region. Cyclic voltammetry on the complexes shows two irreversible oxidations within 0.65 to 1.15 V vs SCE and an irreversible reduction within -1.13 to -1.35 V vs SCE. DFT and TDDFT calculations have been carried out to explain the electronic spectral, as well as electrochemical, observations.

Keywords : N-(Aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines, ruthenium(0), N-H bond activation, crystal structure, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Introduction

The chemistry of ruthenium has been receiving considerable current attention¹, largely because of the interesting properties exhibited by the complexes of this metal. As properties of the complexes are dictated primarily by the coordination environment around the metal center, complexation of ruthenium by ligands of selected types has been of significant importance. Herein we have selected a group of imine-ligands (HL-R), derived from pyrrole-2-aldehyde and *para*-substituted anilines. The selected ligands are known to bind to metal ions, via loss of the N-H proton, as mono-anionic NN-donors forming stable five-membered chelate ring (I)². Coordination chemistry of the selected imine-ligands, containing the pyrrole fragment, is of particular interest with reference to its relevance in biological processes³. It may be mentioned here that while coordination chemistry of the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines with few transition and non-transition metal ions has received some attention², that with

ruthenium appears to have remained less explored⁴. We have recently observed an interesting reaction of the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines upon their interaction with iridium(I), whereby oxidative insertion of the metal center into the pyrrole N-H fragment takes place^{2h}. Prompted by this observation, we got interested to explore the interaction of the selected imine-ligands with another low-valent d⁸ metal center, viz. ruthenium(0). As the source of ruthenium(0) the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃] complex has been chosen, because of its demonstrated ability to undergo facile oxidative insertion reaction with ligands having acidic fragments affording stable mixed-ligand hexacoordinated complexes⁵. The primary objective of the present study has been to examine whether the ruthenium(0) center in [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃] can oxidatively insert into the N-H bond of the selected imine-ligands to afford hydrido-complexes of ruthenium. Reaction of the selected imine-ligands (HL-R) with [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃] has indeed been found to af-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

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ford a family of interesting complexes of ruthenium. The chemistry of all these complexes is reported here, with special reference to their formation, characterization and, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Ruthenium trichloride was purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]$ was synthesized by following a reported procedure⁶. Pyrrole-2-aldehyde was purchased from Spectrochem, Kolkata, India. Triphenylphosphine and the *para*-substituted anilines were purchased from S.D. Fine-Chem Limited, Mumbai, India. The *N*-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines were prepared by condensing pyrrole-2-aldehyde with *para*-substituted anilines in hot ethanol. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received. Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBHP), obtained from Aldrich, and AR grade acetonitrile, procured from Merck, India, were used for electrochemical work. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Syntheses of complexes :

The $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes were obtained by following a general procedure. Specific details are given below for a particular complex.

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-OCH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$: *N*-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)pyrrole-2-alimine (28 mg, 0.10 mmol) was dissolved in warm toluene (40 ml). A stream of nitrogen was passed through this solution for 5 min, and then $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]$ (100 mg, 0.10 mmol) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h under a nitrogen atmosphere to yield a yellowish-brown solution. The solvent was then evaporated and the solid mass, thus obtained,

was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. With hexane : benzene (1 : 1) as the eluant, a yellow band separated, which was extracted with acetonitrile. Evaporation of the acetonitrile extract gave $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-OCH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ as a yellow crystalline solid. Yield : 69%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{49}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{P}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 68.93; H, 4.92; N, 3.28. Found : C, 68.80; H, 4.95; N, 3.24%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3)⁷ : δ -11.31 (t, hydride, *J* 21.0), 3.81 (OCH_3), 5.74 (H, d, *J* 2.3), 6.17 (s, azomethine), 6.33 (H, d, *J* 3.3), 6.50 (2H, d, *J* 8.8), 6.63 (2H, d, *J* 8.8), 7.13–7.35 (2 PPh_3 +H)*; IR : 2016, 1910, 1607, 1567, 1505, 1478, 1433, 1387, 1342, 1308, 1288, 1275, 1249, 1222, 1183, 1111, 1088, 1033, 999, 895, 831, 800, 745, 735, 694, 618, 601, 577, 566, 538, 519, 497 and 459 cm^{-1} .

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$: Yield : 71%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{49}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_2\text{OP}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 70.25; H, 4.92; N, 3.28. Found : C, 70.09; H, 4.86; N, 3.44%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ -11.31 (t, hydride, *J* 21.3), 2.31 (s, CH_3), 5.73 (H, d, *J* 1.8), 6.18 (s, azomethine), 6.33 (H, d, *J* 3.3), 6.48 (2H, d, *J* 4.8), 6.89 (2H, d, *J* 4.8), 7.13–7.39 (2 PPh_3 +H)*; IR : 2022, 1921, 1568, 1506, 1481, 1434, 1388, 1299, 1186, 1091, 1037, 887, 821, 799, 741, 694, 600, 541 and 518 cm^{-1} .

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-H})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$: Yield : 67%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_2\text{OP}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 69.98; H, 4.86; N, 3.40. Found : C, 70.09; H, 4.86; N, 3.44%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ -11.31 (t, hydride, *J* 21.1), 5.76 (H, d, *J* 2.2), 6.13 (s, azomethine), 6.35 (H, d, *J* 2.5), 6.52 (2H, d, *J* 4.7), 6.64 (2H, t, *J* 4.6), 7.15–7.37 (2 PPh_3 +2H)*; IR : 2024, 1940, 1612, 1567, 1507, 1481, 1434, 1386, 1299, 1186, 1092, 1036, 887, 799, 743, 695, 601, 542 and 519 cm^{-1} .

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-Cl})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$: Yield : 72%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_2\text{OP}_2\text{ClRu}$: C, 67.17; H, 4.54; N, 3.26. Found : C, 67.26; H, 4.56; N, 3.24%; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ -11.41 (t, hydride, *J* 21.0), 5.75 (H, d, *J* 2.1), 6.17 (s, azomethine), 6.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.4), 6.69 (2H, d, *J* 8.4), 7.15–7.40 (2 PPh_3 +2H)*; IR : 2029, 1914, 1610, 1570, 1505, 1482, 1434, 1387, 1300, 1187, 1090, 1036, 896, 822, 800, 742, 695, 601, 542 and 518 cm^{-1} .

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1 balance. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra recorded in CDCl_3 solution on

a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-630 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were made using a CH Instruments model 600A electrochemical analyzer. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in the cyclic voltammetry experiments. All electrochemical experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and are uncorrected for junction potentials. Geometry optimization by the density functional theory (DFT) method and electronic spectral analysis for the TDDFT calculations were performed using the Gaussian 03 (B3LYP/SDD-6-31G) package⁸.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of the [Ru(L-CH₃)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)] complex were grown by slow evaporation of solvent from a solution of the complex in acetonitrile. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffracto-

meter using graphite monochromated MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). X-Ray data reduction and, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs⁹. The structure was solved by the direct methods.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

As delineated in the introduction, the primary objective of the present work has been to study the interaction of the selected N-(4'-R-phenyl)pyrrole-2-aldehydes (**HL-R**) with ruthenium(0) and see how they bind to the metal center. The four different substituents, with different electron-withdrawing properties, have been chosen to study their influence, if any, on the redox properties of the resulting complexes. Reactions of the selected imine-ligands (**HL-R**) with [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃] proceed smoothly in refluxing toluene to afford a group of yellow complexes in decent yields. Preliminary characterizations (microanalysis, IR, NMR, etc.) on these complexes indicate presence of a deprotonated imine-ligand, a hydride, a carbonyl and two triphenylphosphines in the coordination sphere. Hence these complexes are formulated in general as [Ru(L-R)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)]. In order to find out stereochemistry of these complexes, as well as to ascertain coordination mode of the imine-ligands in them, structure of a representative member from the series, viz. [Ru(L-CH₃)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)], has been determined by X-ray crystallography. The structure is shown in Fig. 1 and some relevant bond parameters are listed in Table 2. The structure shows that the N-(phenyl)pyrrole-2-aldehyde is coordinated to ruthenium, via cleavage of the N-H bond, as a bidentate NN-donor forming a five-membered chelate ring (**I**). Two triphenylphosphines, a hydride and a carbonyl are also coordinated to the metal center. The coordinated pyrrole-2-aldehyde, hydride and carbonyl have constituted an equatorial plane with the metal at the center, where the hydride is *trans* to the imine-nitrogen and the carbonyl is *trans* to the pyrrole-nitrogen. The two triphenylphosphines have occupied the remaining two axial positions, and hence they are mutually *trans*. The anionic character of the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldehyde and the hydride ligands indicate that ruthenium is in +2 oxidation state in this complex. The Ru-H, Ru-N, Ru-P and Ru-C distances are quite normal, and so are the distances within

Table 1. Crystallographic data for the [Ru(L-CH₃)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)] complex

Empirical formula	C ₄₉ H ₄₂ N ₂ OP ₂ Ru
Formula mass	837.86
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c
<i>a</i> (Å)	12.1720(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	19.8362(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.2383(4)
β (deg)	103.390(1)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	4048.98(17)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (g/cm ⁻³)	1.375
<i>F</i> (000)	1728
Crystal size (mm)	0.10 × 0.15 × 0.29
<i>T</i> (K)	273
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.506
R1 ^a	0.0279
wR2 ^b	0.0829
GOF ^c	0.83

$${}^a R_1 = \frac{\sum |F_o| - |F_c|}{\sum |F_o|}, \quad {}^b wR_2 = \frac{[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}}{\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o^2)^2]}^{1/2}$$

^cGOF = $[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (M - N)]^{1/2}$, where M is the number of reflections and N is the number of parameters refined.

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex (except the coordinated hydride, all other hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity) and (b) view of the equatorial plane.

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles for the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex

Bond distances (Å)			
Ru(1)-P(1)	2.3424(5)	C(4)-N(1)	1.385(2)
Ru(1)-P(2)	2.3389(5)	C(4)-C(5)	1.407(3)
Ru(1)-N(1)	2.1137(14)	C(5)-N(2)	1.303(2)
Ru(1)-N(2)	2.2151(15)	C(6)-N(2)	1.420(2)
Ru(1)-C(100)	1.839(2)	C(100)-O(100)	1.154(2)
Ru(1)-H(100)	1.58(2)		
Bond angles (deg)			
P(1)-Ru(1)-P(2)	168.39(2)	N(1)-Ru(1)-N(2)	76.05(5)
N(1)-Ru(1)-C(100)	175.51(8)	Ru(1)-C(100)-O(100)	179.04(19)
N(2)-Ru(1)-H(100)	165.3(8)		

the chelated imine-ligand. As all the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes have been synthesized similarly and they show similar properties (*vide infra*), the other three $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes (with $\text{R} \neq \text{CH}_3$) are assumed to have similar structures as the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex.

Formation of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes containing ruthenium(II), from reaction between the N-(4'-R-phenyl)pyrrole-2-aldimines and the ruthenium(0) center in $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]$, has been quite interesting. Some speculated sequences behind formation of these complexes, that seem probable, are illustrated in Scheme 1. In the initial step the imine-nitrogen of the **HL-R** ligand is believed to bind to the metal center in $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]$, via displacement of two carbonyl ligands¹⁰, to generate an intermediate **A-R**. This brings the pyrrole N-H fragment of the coordinated imine-ligand in close proximity to the ruthenium(0) center, which eventually leads to oxidative insertion of ruthenium into the N-H bond affording the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex. Such N-H bond activation, mediated by ruthenium(0), is, to our knowledge, unprecedented in the literature.

Scheme 1. Probable steps behind formation of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L}-\text{R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes.

Spectral studies :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that all the ruthenium complexes are diamagnetic, which corresponds to the +2 oxidation state of ruthenium (low-spin d^6 , $S = 0$) in these complexes. ^1H NMR spectra of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes show broad signals within 7.13–7.40 ppm for the coordinated PPh_3 ligands. The hydride signal is observed around -11.3 ppm as a distinct triplet due to coupling with two equivalent phosphorus nuclei with a coupling constant of ~ 21 Hz. Signals for the methoxy and methyl groups in the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-OCH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes are observed respectively at 3.81 and 2.31 ppm. Most of the expected aromatic proton signals, as well as the azomethine-proton signal, from the coordinated imine-ligand are clearly observed in the expected region, while a few could not be detected due to their overlap with other signals in the same region.

Infrared spectrum of each $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex shows many bands of different intensities in the $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. No attempt has been made to assign each individual band to a specific vibration. However, comparison with the spectra of the corresponding uncoordinated ligands shows that the N-H stretch, observed in the uncoordinated ligands near 3211 cm^{-1} , is

absent in the complexes. In all the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes, a very strong band observed within $1910\text{--}1940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the coordinated CO, and a moderately strong band displayed near 2022 cm^{-1} is attributable to the coordinated hydride. Three strong bands have been observed near 518 , 695 and 742 cm^{-1} in all the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes indicating the presence of coordinated PPh_3 ligands. Several sharp bands (e.g. near 1607 , 1505 , 1388 , 1303 , 1244 , 1035 , 830 , 799 , 600 and 541 cm^{-1}) are also observed in the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes, which were absent in the $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})_3]$ complex, and hence these are attributed to the coordinated imine-ligand.

All the complexes are found to be readily soluble in acetone, dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing yellow solutions. Electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded in dichloromethane solution. Each complex shows intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. Spectral data are presented in Table 3. To have an insight into the nature of these absorptions, geometry of a representative complex, viz. $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$, was initially optimized by the DFT method and then electronic spectral analysis was carried out by TDDFT calculations. The results of the TDDFT calculations are presented in Table 4 and com-

Table 3. Electronic spectral and cyclic voltammetric data

Complex	Electronic spectral data ^a	Cyclic voltammetric data ^b
	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$)	E (V) vs SCE
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-OCH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$	383 (15800), 261 (16900)	1.05^c , 0.65^c , -1.31^d
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$	388 (15900), 263 (17000)	1.11^c , 0.71^c , -1.13^d
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-H})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$	382 (17400), 264 (18300)	1.15^c , 0.70^c , -1.35^d
$[\text{Ru}(\text{L-Cl})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$	380 (17300), 268 (28000)	0.94^c , 0.75^c , -1.15^d

^aIn dichloromethane. ^bSolvent, acetonitrile; supporting electrolyte, TBHP; scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1} . ^c E_{pa} value. ^d E_{pc} value.

Table 4. Computed parameters from TDDFT calculations on $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex for electronic spectral properties in dichloromethane solution

Excited state	Composition	CI	E (eV)	Oscillator strength (f)	λ_{theo} (nm)	Assignments	λ_{exp} (nm)
1	H \rightarrow L	0.24049	3.4704	0.0794	357.26	MLCT/LLCT	383
	H \rightarrow L+1	0.63089				LMCT/LLCT	
2	H-2 \rightarrow L+5	0.10309	4.7478	0.0027	261.14	MLCT/LLCT/ILCT	261
	H-1 \rightarrow L+9	0.37160				MLCT/LLCT/ILCT	
	H-1 \rightarrow L+11	-0.13491				MLCT/LLCT/ILCT	
	H-1 \rightarrow L+12	0.10409				MLCT/LLCT/ILCT	
	H \rightarrow L+15	0.22957				MLCT/LMCT/LLCT	
	H \rightarrow L+16	0.21360				MLCT/LMCT/LLCT	
H \rightarrow L+18	0.36067				MLCT/LMCT/LLCT		

positions of the orbitals associated with the spectral transitions are given in Table 5. Contour plots of the two frontier orbitals, viz. the highest occupied molecular orbital (H) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (L), are shown in Fig. 2. The lowest energy absorption near 383 nm is attributable to a combination of $H \rightarrow L$

Table 5. Compositions of all molecular orbitals of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex associated with the electronic spectral transitions

Molecular orbital	% Contribution of fragments			
	Ru	L-CH ₃	CO	PPh ₃
H-2	34.5	30.6	10.0	24.9
H-1	30.9	38.1	7.5	23.5
H	12.0	80.6	1.5	6.9
L	5.2	89.4	4.39	3.1
L+1	12.1	4.5	1.1	82.3
L+5	3.7	1.1	0.8	94.4
L+9	4.3	6.4	4.4	84.9
L+11	4.1	40.1	4.4	51.4
L+12	3.9	40.0	4.0	52.1
L+15	15.4	35.5	19.6	29.5
L+16	17.6	39.1	5.4	37.9
L+18	22.1	44.1	25.6	8.2

Fig. 2. Contour plot of the HOMO and LUMO of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complex.

and $H \rightarrow L+1$ transitions, and based on the nature of the participating orbitals the same is assignable to a mixture of LLCT, MLCT and LMCT transitions, involving primarily the imine ligand, with much less contribution from the metal center. The next absorption around 264 nm is found to be a combination of $H-2 \rightarrow L+5$, $H-1 \rightarrow L+9$, $H-1 \rightarrow L+11$, $H-1 \rightarrow L+12$, $H \rightarrow L+15$, $H \rightarrow L+16$ and $H \rightarrow L+18$ transitions, and is assignable to an admixture of ILCT, LLCT, MLCT and LMCT transitions, with varying contributions from the metal and surrounding ligands. It is interesting to note here that the dominant nature of MLCT transition, usually found in complexes of ruthenium(II) with imine-ligands, is not observed in the present group of complexes.

Electrochemical properties :

Electrochemical properties of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-R})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ complexes have been studied by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP). Voltammetric data are given in Table 3 and a selected voltammogram is shown in Fig. 3. Each complex shows two oxidative responses on the positive side of SCE and a

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-CH}_3)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{H})]$ in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP) at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} .

reductive response on the negative side. All the responses are irreversible in nature, and while the oxidative responses are found to be one-electron in nature, the reductive response shows non-stoichiometric current. In view of composition of the HOMO in all these complexes, the first oxidative response is assigned to oxidation of the coordinated imine-ligand. Similarly, based on the composition of the LUMO, the reduction is assigned to re-

duction of the coordinated imine-ligand. Potential of the redox responses in the [Ru(L-R)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)] complexes does not show any systematic variation with the nature of the substituent R in the imine-ligand.

Conclusion

The present study shows that the N-(aryl)pyrrole-2-aldimines undergo facile N-H bond activation, mediated by the ruthenium(0) center in [Ru(PPh₃)₂(CO)₃], leading to the formation of hydrido-complexes of ruthenium(II) of type [Ru(L-R)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(H)]. Presence of both hydride and carbonyl in these complexes indicates their possible utilization as catalysts for useful organic transformations, which is currently under investigation.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance received from the Department of Science and Technology, Government of West Bengal, Kolkata [Sanction No. 746(Sanc.)/ST/P/S&T/2G-4/2013] is gratefully acknowledged. The authors thank Dr. Saurabh Das (Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University) for his help in recording the electronic spectra of the complexes.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC 1431051.

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